

A pan-European analysis on exposure to greenery during active travel – insights from using open mobility data

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Abstract. Contact to urban greenery has numerous well-studied benefits for human health and wellbeing. While most research has focused on residential approaches, exposure assessments including people’s mobility have emerged only in recent years. This work in progress presents an approach to comparing urban scale exposures to greenery during active travel on a pan-European level, using bike sharing data and Strava global heatmap.

Keywords: mobility, active travel, environmental exposure, NDVI, green space

1. Background

There is a growing body of evidence revealing the benefits of urban greenery on human health and wellbeing as well as sustainable transportation systems. These benefits occur both in residential and in mobility contexts (Liu et al., 2023). While residential exposure to greenery has been extensively studied, research related to quantifying mobility-related exposure has only been emerging during recent years. In travel contexts, exposure to greenery is still underrepresented compared to air quality or noise (Poom et al., 2021).

To assess exposure to travel greenery, studies are commonly relying on individual GPS tracks gathered from participants (Liu et al., 2023). While this method allows the assessment of individual exposures for a small population sample within a study area, collecting comparative GPS data across multiple study areas and over entire cities remains challenging and costly.

Research access to mobile big data revealing people’s realized mobilities on population-scale is often complicated due to the sensitive nature of loca-

Published in “Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Location Based Services (LBS 2025)”, edited by Juha Oksanen, Henrikki Tenkanen, Pyry Kettunen and Ville Mäkinen, LBS 2025 7-9 May 2025 Otaniemi, Espoo, Finland.

This contribution underwent double-blind peer review based on the paper. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15352894>
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tion-based data or the data being owned by companies with mainly commercial interests (Haraguchi et al., 2022). Finding ways to make use of openly available data containing mobility information would thus contribute to more comprehensive assessments of people’s environmental exposures during mobility and enable large-scale comparisons of these mobility and exposure patterns.

Some open-access datasets have the potential to reveal realized urban mobility and environmental exposure patterns. For example, extensive bike sharing trip data is openly available in several major European cities. Another example is Strava global heatmap which is available globally in a spatial resolution that allows for street-wise urban mobility analysis. Both these datasets are explicitly capturing active travel movements, which makes them particularly useful for assessing environmental exposures.

In this ongoing research, we aim to use spatially extensive and open big data to reveal patterns of exposure to greenery and usage of urban green spaces during active travel mobility in European cities. Our focus in this study lies on the large-scale applicability and on the use of realized mobility data.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Greenery

We are using the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) to assess the availability of greenery in urban areas. NDVI is commonly used in urban green space studies and has been associated with health benefits as well as both perceived greenness and perceived pleasantness of places. It is also an increasingly used indicator in travel greenery contexts.

NDVI at 10m resolution has been retrieved from the openEO API with its underlying Sentinel-2 L2A satellite imagery. To account for differences in seasonal variations throughout varying geographical and climatic contexts and between different years, we calculated monthly NDVI over a five year timespan (2018-2022).

2.2. Mobility patterns

Strava global heatmap for bike rides is used as a source for realized cycling mobility patterns in the study cities. It indicates relative usage of roads and paths for cycling over a one-year timespan in resolutions of up to 2.3m. The data can be imported into QGIS as XYZ tiles and further extracted locally. The extracted rasters are used to derive cycling intensity by interpreting the

resulting raster band values (Dong et al., 2023). A very high spearman correlation ($\rho=0.84$) with absolute cycling volumes from Strava Metro in Helsinki indicates the usability of Strava heatmap for deriving relative path usage. Strava data is known to have demographic biases, yet it has been deemed useful to reveal spatial variation of cycling intensity (e.g. Venter et al., 2023)

Origin-destination trip records from bike sharing systems are openly available capturing several years of bike sharing mobility in major European cities in varying geographical contexts, such as Helsinki, Glasgow, London, Munich, Madrid, etc. These datasets are collected by the system operators in the mentioned cities¹ and include origin and destination of the cycling trips, not however the individual route trajectories. Yet, they reveal realized patterns of where people cycle in the city. The provided timestamps allow for a time-sensitive analysis of greenery exposure accounting for seasonal dynamics.

2.3. Analysis

Cycling intensity obtained from Strava global heatmap can be combined with surrounding NDVI values to derive how Strava users' mobility exposes them to greenery on a city-level. This can be achieved by aggregating cycling intensity from the raster to OpenStreetMap segments and buffering them by 30m to derive segment-wise cycling activity and available greenery. These segment-wise values can be aggregated to city-level and finally the resulting city-level exposure value is available greenery weighted by cycling activity.

From bike sharing data, individual route exposures can be assessed. As the data does not contain route trajectories, GREENPATHS2.0², which is building on the *r5py* library (Fink et al., 2022) for routing, is used as routing and exposure assessment tool. GREENPATHS allows routing trips based on different measures. Routing based on travel time (shortest routes) between origin and destination and comparing these to other available route options can reveal spatial inequalities in exposure and potential access to green travel environments (Willberg et al., 2023). Using the monthly NDVI data, this analysis can be carried out accounting for seasonal shifts in both the amount of trips and the greenness of the environments in the given month.

¹ e.g. <https://www.hsl.fi/en/hsl/open-data> (Helsinki) or <https://cycling.data.tfl.gov.uk/> (London)

² <https://green-paths-2.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

3. Expected results

We aim to provide an assessment of exposure to greenery during active travel in large European cities, using realized mobility data. The final results can provide information on the city-level exposure to greenery that active travelers experience in the study cities. The results can also reveal whether there are observable latitudinal patterns in greenery exposure throughout Europe given differences in seasonal variations in greenery. Furthermore, the final results will support spatial planners in providing the benefits of green spaces more equitably to the citizens, including during their everyday travel.

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